

EVIDENCE-BASED EXPLORATION OF INFECTION PREVENTION PRACTICES AMONG HEMODIALYSIS NURSES

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the infection prevention practices among hemodialysis nurses in private and government dialysis centers in Eastern Pangasinan. It tackled their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in hemodialysis centers, relevant training for the past two years, and category of health facility. The study utilized the quantitative and qualitative research design, as well as a survey questionnaire and structured interview guide questions, as the primary tools for gathering data. In terms of the qualitative aspect, the narration of the responses was noted down. In the quantitative aspect, several statistical tools were used, such as frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test, and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). The nurse respondents were young adults, female-dominated, bachelor's degree holders, had been in the dialysis center for 3-4 years, had attended a few numbers of seminars, and were employed in private dialysis centers. The extent of nurses' practices in the prevention of nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients is highest during hemodialysis, followed by after hemodialysis, and lowest before dialysis. Significant differences were noted in terms of age, civil status, and number of years in service. The age of nurses affects their practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients before, during, and after hemodialysis. Married nurses significantly provide a higher level of practice in preventing nosocomial infection than single nurses. The number of years of service affects the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection after hemodialysis. The lower the level of the highest educational attainment of the nurses, the more they practice the proper prevention of nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis. It implies that even those who have a bachelor's degree render the correct practices in the prevention of nosocomial infection.

INTRODUCTION

It happens in a healthcare facility that nosocomial infection sets in among patients. It is a significant risk to patient and staff safety. Hemodialysis (HD) patients and dialysis staff are vulnerable to healthcare-associated infections due to frequent and prolonged exposures in the Hemodialysis environment. The increased risk is mainly related to the immune-compromised status of dialysis patients, frequent and prolonged blood exposure during Hemodialysis treatments through vascular access and extracorporeal circuit, proximity to other patients during treatment in the Hemodialysis facility, frequent contact with healthcare workers, who frequently move between patients and between machines, frequent hospitalization and surgery, and non-adherence or breaks in the practices (Karkar, 2018). It clearly shows that nosocomial infections happen in hemodialysis centers because patients are more vulnerable due to lower body resistance. Health workers are also prone to infections due to their continuous exposure to patients.

Waste management needles should be disposed of in closed, unbreakable containers. A "no touch" technique should be used to drop the needle into the container. If this is difficult due to the design of the container, staff should complete patient care before disposing of needles. Nurses should be involved in multi-professional discussions where decisions are made about changes in patient treatment. Nurses must have the clinical skills and competencies to manage renal patients in different stages of their illness. Many infection control measures, such as appropriate hand hygiene, consistent use of aseptic technique, cleaning, and disinfection practices, are simple but require staff accountability and behavioural change, in addition to improving staff education, reporting, and surveillance systems. Infection control and prevention is the responsibility of the nurse and represents an integral element of the patients' safety program. It encompasses the processes and activities that identify and reduce the risks of acquiring and transmitting infections among individuals. Therefore, nurses should have professional and ethical responsibilities to make sure that their knowledge and skills regarding infection control are up-to-date and that they practice safely and competently (Uoda, 2019). It is also the responsibility of the health workers to dispose of used needles and other equipment used in Hemodialysis. Hospitals are provided with trash bins that are color-coded depending on the category of the waste material. Aside from this, the health care worker must practice proper hand hygiene, which is the simplest way of preventing infection.

Dialysis is a life-saving treatment for patients of all ages with end-stage kidney diseases. Infection prevention and control in an artificial kidney unit or a dialysis setting is essential to protecting the health of these vulnerable patients. Hemodialysis is a life-saving treatment, but dialysis carries the risk of infection that could be life-threatening, which requires strict adherence to infection prevention, including hand hygiene. Since hemodialysis does the work of the kidneys by cleansing a patient's blood, a lack of infection prevention and control could result in a life-threatening infection. Infection is a leading cause of hospitalization and the second leading cause of death for dialysis

patients. Life-threatening infections that could occur through dialysis include: During dialysis, patients could spread respiratory viruses among each other and health care workers without the proper infection prevention processes in place. Diseases such as COVID-19 and influenza can spread in a dialysis clinic. You can reduce the risk of this spread with proper hand hygiene, including the use of alcohol-based hand sanitizer, personal protective equipment such as face masks, and educating patients to practice respiratory hygiene such as coughing or sneezing into the inside of the elbow to avoid droplet spray or using a tissue, disposing of the tissue immediately after use, and cleaning hands after coughing or sneezing. Dialysis facilities should provide tissues and hand sanitizers for patients and visitors to comply with respiratory hygiene. Patients with upper respiratory symptoms should be provided (Perri, 2022). The healthcare worker needs to safeguard themselves in the HD center. The use of personal protective equipment is necessary to prevent transmission of infection while attending to their patients. Aside from hand washing, they can still use hand sanitizers or alcohol to kill the microbes.

Patients with end-stage renal disease (End Stage Renal Disease) are vulnerable to infectious diseases due to their impaired immunity and high risk of exposure to pathogens. Dialysis patients are prone to bloodborne infections transmitted through needles, transfusions, and dialysis catheters. It is essential to establish infection control measures to prevent the transmission of pathogens in hemodialysis facilities. The infection prevention and management program should include infection surveillance and monitoring processes, strategy development to reduce or minimize the risk of infection and evaluation and feedback processes for redesigning and implementing the revised program.

The dialysis room should be monitored for a certain period so that infection control issues can be identified in terms of the units, infection sites, microorganisms, and others. Ongoing surveillance activities may identify health-associated events or problems about which recommendations and action plans can be developed to minimize infection transmission and reduce future incidents (Park et al., 2018). The Hemodialysis centers must enhance their infection control protocols to minimize the incidence of infections among their patients. Proper monitoring and evaluation of their services must be done regularly to improve their services.

Gloves are to be worn for touching blood and body fluids, mucous membranes, or non-intact skin of all patients; for handling items or surfaces soiled with blood or body fluids; and for performing vascular access procedures where blood spill is likely. Gloves should also be worn when touching the patient's equipment or other environmental surfaces. Disposable gloves are for single use only and come in a variety of materials, such as vinyl, latex, and nitrile. Gloves are to be changed and hands washed after contact with each patient, whenever the gloves are bloodstained, and after handling infectious waste containers. Hand hygiene should be performed using soap and water or alcohol-based antiseptic hand rubs. Sharps containers should not be mounted too high but should be easily accessible. They also should not be allowed to overfill (Cuison, 2020). The HD center must have adequate personal protective equipment supplies for their healthcare

workers, particularly disposable consumables because transmission of infection is very high. Fluid splashes can happen during the procedure, so the healthcare worker must be careful when handling discharges.

To minimize the need for emergency mouth-to-mouth resuscitation, mouthpieces, pocket masks, resuscitation bags, or other ventilation devices should be available for use in areas where the need for resuscitation is predictable. Masks and goggles or full-face shields shall be worn during any procedure likely to generate droplets, blood splashes, or body fluids near the face. Masks should fully cover the nose and mouth. Goggles should fit snugly over and around the eyes. Personal eyewear, such as prescription glasses, is not a substitute for protective eyewear. Face shields should cover the forehead, extend below the chin, and wrap around the side of the face when worn correctly. Initiating and terminating dialysis and troubleshooting vascular access may increase a healthcare worker's risk of exposure to bloodborne pathogens.

The Hemodialysis setting presents a challenge for environmental cleaning and disinfection because of the demand for rapid turnover of stations. Dialysis center staff often feel rushed to complete tasks, especially when transitioning patients on or off machines. Under these pressures, personnel may eliminate or take shortcuts in steps essential for preventing infection transmission. If contaminated surfaces turned over quickly are not adequately cleaned and disinfected, bloodborne and other pathogens may remain alive and infectious for days. Dialysis centers should allow adequate time between patients for thorough cleaning and disinfection.

All surfaces of the dialysis station, including the machine and patient chair, should be cleaned and disinfected using a hospital disinfectant. Cleaning and disinfection should commence once the patient has left the station to prevent cross-contamination. Internal surfaces of the dialysis machine should be regularly disinfected following the manufacturer's instructions. Written protocols outlining the steps should be in place, and using a log can help document and keep track of cleaning and disinfection. Clean and contaminated areas should be separated in the facility, with clean supplies and medication preparation areas having adequate spatial separation from contaminated equipment storage (Cuison, 2020). Proper equipment cleaning must be done after each procedure to be ready with the following scheduled patients. Sterilization is usually done to used equipment to make it sterile and safe for patient use.

The proximity of patients on dialysis to one another and healthcare workers can increase the transmission of infection. Standard precautions can reduce the risk of transmission of many common germs when used for every patient encounter across the continuum of care. The practices included in standard precautions are hand hygiene, use of personal protective equipment, respiratory hygiene, appropriate patient placement, careful handling of textiles and laundry, and safe injection practices. Chief among these is hand hygiene, which has long been a cornerstone of infection prevention and control. Alcohol-based hand sanitizer is more convenient and efficient than handwashing with soap and water and is the preferred hand-sanitizing product for these types of care settings. (Millson, 2022). Nosocomial infections can be reduced once the equipment is

cleaned vigorously, and proper packing and storage must be done. Proper hand hygiene practice is an action by health workers to lessen the transmission of infection.

According to Vijayan and Boyce (2018), outbreaks of infections in hemodialysis centers continue to occur due to poor infection control practices. Patients with End Stage Kidney Disease treated with Hemodialysis are at substantially increased risk of life-threatening infections. Most bloodstream infections are related to vascular access, of which 70% are associated with using a central venous catheter. Infections result in significant morbidity and are second only to cardiovascular diseases as a cause of mortality in patients with End Stage Kidney Disease. Patients on Hemodialysis are susceptible to viral infections, including hepatitis B, hepatitis C, HIV, and influenza. Lapses in infection control practices, such as hand hygiene and environmental cleaning, have been associated with bloodstream infections and HCV outbreaks. The Centers for Disease Control strongly recommends several infection control procedures, including hand hygiene, appropriate catheter care, antiseptic agents, checklists, and staff and patient education, all of which are vital to reducing infections. Dialysis personnel should be thoroughly trained in Standard Precautions and other infection control measures. It is vital that healthcare workers strictly follow infection control protocols.

According to the Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2023), the dialysis facility environment may be a source of infection transmission. Inadequately cleaned and disinfected dialysis stations, Hemodialysis machines, effluent drain wall boxes, and other equipment have been implicated in transmitting pathogens in Hemodialysis facilities.

The CDC provides detailed guidelines and checklists for disinfecting dialysis stations, emphasizing that this process should occur once patients have exited the Hemodialysis unit. Single-dose and multi-dose medication vials are also essential in preventing infection transmission. Single-use should only be accessed once, and multi-dose vials should be dedicated to one patient whenever possible. Medications and saline syringes should be prepared in a dedicated, clean, separate area in the dialysis unit and taken to individual stations by hand. A medication cart should not be used to take medications from station to station because this has been associated with the transmission of infections. Reuse of dialyzers has been associated with outbreaks of gram-negative bloodstream infections, and reuse facilities must ensure strict adherence to sterilization protocol to mitigate the risk of infection transmission.

In the study conducted by Bayoumi et al. (2019) among nurses on infection control practices, the overall nurses' performance regarding infection control at enrolled dialysis units demonstrated that half of the nurses had met most steps. In addition, the first and second observations showed that nurses ignored hand hygiene and needed to be committed to wearing clean gloves as needed. The practice of hand hygiene is not taken for granted because they are exposed to body fluids from their patients, which might be a source of transmission of infection.

In the findings of Sugawara et al. (2021) on the measures for the prevention of infection in dialysis units, half of the responding facilities were hospitals with multiple

departments, and the other half were clinics specialized in dialysis. Several infection prevention measures, such as health checks of staff and patients, donning of masks before and after Hemodialysis, and disinfection of frequently contacted areas, were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic. There was a significant improvement in the implementation rate of these measures during the pandemic, compared to before, which reached over 90%. More than half of the facilities reported a shortage of disposable masks and hand sanitizer alcohol. Isolation of COVID-19 patients in private rooms was possible only in 52.7% of the facilities. Most facilities could not accept COVID-19 dialysis patients due to insufficient space and workforce. Nosocomial transmission of COVID-19 occurred in 4.0% of the facilities. Of those infected, 51.9% were staff.

It revealed that most hemodialysis facilities in Japan had improved implementation of infection control measures and had a shortage of PPEs and disinfectants, though some facilities did not implement infection prevention measures adequately, mainly due to their limited space. It may be recommended that each facility immediately establish isolation measures to prepare for the pandemic of COVID-19.

Patients with chronic kidney disease on hemodialysis are often at risk for infection, and the key role of the nursing team, active in the nephrology unit, is to have extensive knowledge about the principles of infection control. The study focused on nursing care aimed at preventing infection in patients undergoing Hemodialysis.

It showed 11 nursing care sessions directed at preventing vascular access infection, especially with the central venous catheter. They identified four articles with ten general care on preventing infection in hemodialysis patients. Finally, care is directed to surveillance policies to prevent infection in hemodialysis patients (Brandao et al., 2018). It must be part of the protocol of Hemodialysis centers to revisit their infection control policies to identify gaps in their old policies. Healthcare workers must also be trained on Hemodialysis updates to improve their nursing care for their patients.

Qin et al. (2021) found in their study that the mask-wearing rate of patients increased. Hand sanitizer consumption increased significantly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Hand hygiene compliance rates increased in physicians, nurses, and other employees before the pandemic. The incidences of UTRI and pneumonia decreased during the pandemic. Notably, catheter-related, and digestive tract infections also decreased during the pandemic. As a result, the incidences of UTRI, pneumonia, catheter-related infections, digestive tract infections, and other sites decreased during the pandemic. The study indicated an association between mandatory mask-wearing and reinforced hand hygiene education and decreased respiratory, catheter-related, and digestive tract infection episodes in the hemodialysis unit.

Uoda (2019) assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding standard precautions concerning Hospital-acquired protection (HAls) among hemodialysis nurses in hemodialysis centers in Mosul.

There were 25 hemodialysis nurses in hemodialysis centers in Mosul. All agreed to participate in the study. Although 72% of the nurses knew that their hands could be a source of infection associated with health care, only 36% of the nursing staff washed their hands before contacting another used 92% of the nursing staff when contacting the patient in the dialysis unit and 40% of nursing staff also wore masks when contacting the patient.

Gloves were used by 98% of the nurses. 46% of the nurses were usually wearing masks when contacting a patient. Books and journals were the primary sources of information about (HAI) among 52% of the nurses. It concluded that the nurses' knowledge of healthcare-related illnesses did not fulfill this purpose because some nursing staff needed to adhere to personal hygiene practices. The necessary training programs for nurses in hemodialysis centers on promoting hygiene standards and optimal use of personal protection against hospital infection were recommended.

Tabash et al. (2018) studied healthcare workers' compliance with infection control in hemodialysis units. They revealed that hospital management needs to practice its role more efficiently in encouraging healthcare providers to comply with infection prevention and control protocols. Most of the study participants needed adequate infection prevention and control protocol training. The findings of the standard precaution showed that the compliance with hand hygiene score was 56.2%, personnel protective equipment score was 87.5%, using waste management score was 39.6%, environmental infection control practices score was 54.3%, and aseptic technique score was 62.8%. However, the additional precaution score was 56.5%.

Moreover, the study revealed that 45.8% of the health care providers were exposed to an injury from used needles or sharp medical instruments. The study also found that 93.5% of the healthcare providers in the hemodialysis unit received the recommended three doses of the hepatitis B vaccine. It concluded that there is a need to develop an infection prevention and control protocol, particularly for the hemodialysis unit. Continuous education and training programs for healthcare staff and physical environmental fitness concerning Infection Prevention and Control protocol should be implemented. Training is essential for the HD staff to be abreast with the latest updates in the care of HD patients.

Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework

The study used the Health Belief model. HBM is a popular model applied in nursing, especially in issues focusing on patient compliance and preventive healthcare practices. The model postulates that health-seeking behavior is influenced by a person's perception of a threat posed by a health problem and the value associated with actions aimed at reducing the threat. The Health Belief Model addresses the relationship between a person's beliefs and behaviors. It provides a way to understand and predict how clients will behave about their health and how they will comply with healthcare therapies.

The nursing goal for patients undergoing hemodialysis includes preventing or minimizing complications, supporting adaptation to change, providing information on the prognosis and treatment regimen that is well understood, and managing pain.

Swanson's Caring Theory was also used to facilitate the Process of "knowing" and "being with" while performing direct nursing care and attentive listening to assist the patient in becoming more open-minded and expressing personal perceptions toward the disease to engage the patient further to increase self-awareness recognition, sense of loss, and negative perceptions. The theories were adapted since they are a good fit for studying clients undergoing dialysis.

Box one- the Input dealt with the profile of respondents and the infection prevention practice for nosocomial infections among patients undergoing hemodialysis. Box two- the Process dealt with data gathering using the questionnaire and the interview guide questions. Box three- the Output tackled the proposed intervention plan to improve the infection prevention practices for nosocomial infections among hemodialysis patient.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study explored the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infections in patients undergoing hemodialysis. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their;
 - a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. civil status;
 - d. highest educational attainment;
 - e. number of years working in a hemodialysis center,
 - f. relevant training has been in hemodialysis for the past two years, and
 - g. category of a health facility?
2. What are the practices of the respondents in preventing nosocomial infections in hemodialysis patients along;
 - a. before hemodialysis;
 - b. during hemodialysis; and
 - c. after hemodialysis?
3. Is there significant difference between the prevention practices in nosocomial infection before, during and after hemodialysis across their profile variables?
4. Is there significant relationship between the prevention practices in nosocomial infection before, during and after hemodialysis across their profile variables?
5. What enhancement program can be proposed to enhance the practices of health workers in the prevention of nosocomial infection?

Null Hypothesis

This study was tested in its null form at 0.05 level of significance that;

1. There is no significant difference between the prevention practices in nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis across their profile variables
 2. There is a significant relationship between the prevention practices in nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis across their profile variables
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METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the research methodology, encompassing discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed the exploratory mixed method and concurrent research design with the questionnaire as a data-gathering tool and structured interview guide questions to explore the prevention practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients. The researcher collects and analyzes qualitative data, leveraging these findings to construct the subsequent quantitative phase. Results were merged during data analysis. Quantitative analysis employs descriptive and inferential statistics, whereas qualitative analyses produce expressive data that provide descriptive details to examine the study's objectives.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study's respondents were hemodialysis nurses in Eastern Pangasinan's public and private dialysis centers. They were present during the data gathering, which consisted of 75 respondents.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized two types of data-gathering methods: The researcher employs a survey questionnaire and a structured interview guide to gather data. A survey questionnaire was based on Millson, 2023 and previous studies and articles related to the study. Part I focused on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years assigned in the dialysis center, and type of facility. Part II explored the prevention practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection in patients undergoing hemodialysis before, during, and after dialysis. Moreover, along with the qualitative part, interview guide questions were made following the sequencing of the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before gathering data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission was granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher submitted the letter of request to the Chief of Hospital/ Medical Director or Head of Dialysis Centers through their Chief Nurses. After securing the permission, the researcher secured consent from the respondents. The researcher collected the data personally.

On the qualitative aspect, the researcher scheduled the interview with selected hemodialysis nurses. However, only 4 HD nurses were available for the interview. The researcher ensured that ethical precautions and procedures were met. In the whole process of this study, the researcher considered ethical precautions to follow.

Treatment of the Data

Frequency and percentage were used for Problem No.1 on the respondent's profile.

The frequency was determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

Formula: $P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$

where: P = percentage

F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

Problem No. 2: The prevention practices of nurses on nosocomial infection in hemodialysis centers—the weighted mean was used before, during, and after dialysis. The weighted mean is the mean of a set of values wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance. This study used a five-point rating scale system, as shown in the table below.

Formula:

The weighted mean is the mean of a set of values wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance.

Formula: $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fi}{N}$

where: "x̄" = weighted mean

N = total # of population; and

fi = frequencies corresponding to the given items.

Literal Value	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Practiced
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Practiced
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Practiced
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Practiced
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Practiced

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the nurse respondents.

Narrations of Participants

Participant No. 1- John

He is a 37-year-old male with a master's degree who has worked in the dialysis center for three years in a *government dialysis center*.

According to John, "Kaming mga nurses dito had undergone training for us to be competent in this field. I ensured we observed the standard precautions to give optimal care to the access site. I prepare the patient for hemodialysis. I prepare all the needed equipment before we start the procedure. I make sure that infection will not set into my patients. I had to do a lot of preparation before the procedure. To control infection, we used solutions to disinfect the tools used. The water supply is adequate in the center, so we do handwashing before and after each procedure. All of us health team members used gloves, masks, haircaps, and other Personal Protective Equipment to ensure that infection transmission would not occur, especially those with infectious comorbidities like Pulmonary Tuberculosis and pneumonia. I made sure to check that patients are vaccinated with flu vaccine and Hepatitis B."

It revealed that the nurses had undergone the necessary training on hemodialysis. It is essential that the nurses be competent in attending to patients undergoing hemodialysis, particularly in preventing infections, since the patients are vulnerable to infections.

During Dialysis

During the procedure, he cited, "I maintained that a limited watcher was present in the room. I managed discharges by making sure there would be no leaks and splashes. To dispose of the discharges, I placed gloves in a sealed container".

He continues, "I take vital signs to ensure the patient is alright. Limited interactions were done, so there will be a focus on the procedure. After dialysis, the patient is prepared for transfer to another bed. The patient is placed in isolation for those with infectious conditions.

During the procedure, the nurses had to protect themselves because, at times, there are splashes of fluids that may happen, and they should be ready with it to avoid transmission of infection, especially if an infectious disease is present in the patient.

After Dialysis

After the procedure, he continued, "I clean the site for fluid splashes, the patient is cleaned from leaks or fluids and transported to the room, and vital signs monitoring is continued. I wash used tools, and proper packing is done before it is autoclaved. Other tools were soaked in Lysol solutions for disinfection."

The participant's response corroborates with the study's findings that the nurses perform prevention practices among patients undergoing hemodialysis. Nurses equally have the skills to care for patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Participant No. 2. Nora

She is 28 years old, single, has a bachelor's degree, has been in the service for 11 months, and works in a private clinic.

During hemodialysis

She narrated, "Before the procedure, I prepared the access site using an aseptic technique using antiseptics. I prepare the patient physically and emotionally so that the patient can cooperate throughout the procedure. I arrange the tools needed, if injury happens, I wash my hands, and reports to the head nurse. Throughout the procedure, we all used personal protective equipment to prevent splashes and infection transmission. We made sure that the environment is maintained to be clean and hygienic."

During the procedure, the nurses have to allay the condition of their patients to have a smooth flow of the procedure and also for them to be cooperative. PPES must be worn for whatever eventualities may arise. They safeguard their patients as well as themselves.

After dialysis

After the procedure, she cited, "I clean the site for any fluid leaks. We use Lysol solutions to soak some equipment. The collected blood samples are extracted, and then I send them to the laboratory."

It shows that the participants' narration is related to the study's findings. It clearly mentions that nurses perform activities to prevent nosocomial infection during hemodialysis.

Participant No. 3-Karlo

He is a 35-year-old male with a bachelor's degree, two years in service, and works in a public hospital.

Before hemodialysis

He narrates, "I do handwashing in the faucet using soap and water. I made sure to use gloves, other personal protective equipment, and a hair cap to protect us from fluid leaks. In the center, we have an adequate supply of antiseptic and alcohols because these are very important."

During hemodialysis

He continued, "I disinfect the site using betadine and alcohol. If an injury happens, I wash with soap and water and report it to the head nurse. We use an N95 mask and other PPEs during the procedure. We continuously check the site while the procedure is going on. If untoward symptoms occur, we refer to the doctor and give whatever treatment is ordered.

Participant No. 4-Myra

She is 39 years old, holds a bachelor's degree, and has been working for 14 years in a private dialysis center.

Before hemodialysis

Before the procedures, he narrated, "I prepare the patient physically and emotionally to win her cooperation during the procedure. The team practices proper handwashing using tap water from the faucet. The whole team uses Personal Protective Equipment during the entire procedure. In the center, we have adequate supplies of tools for the procedure. Those patients with comorbidities are separated from other patients like those with Pulmonary Tuberculosis and pneumonia."

During Hemodialysis

She continues, "Before the start of the procedure, the patient is prepared together with the tools, medications, and solutions. If anything arises during the procedure, like an injury, I report it immediately to the head nurse. In cases of leaks, handwashing is done immediately, and gloves that have been punctured are disposed of. The whole team uses Personal Protective Equipment's to safeguard ourselves from transmission or splashes of fluids."

After hemodialysis

After the procedure, "I prepare the patient for transfer to his bed to monitor vital signs. Once stable, the specimen samples are labeled, and I send them to the laboratory. Patients with infectious illnesses are separated from the others. Then, I wash and cleanse the tools used and prepare them for sterilization. All the used PPEs are discarded immediately and placed in a closed container. If problems occur, we respond immediately to prevent the incidence of complications."

It revealed that the participant nurse's narration corroborates the study's findings. They have common practices in caring for patients undergoing hemodialysis, which goes to show that the nurses are competent.

Respondent's Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service in a dialysis center, number of relevant trainings on hemodialysis for the past two years, and type of health facility.

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that the majority of the respondents are in the age bracket of 31-40 years old, with a frequency of 59 or 78.7 percent, followed by 21-30 years old, with a frequency of 14 or 18.7 percent, and 41-50 with a frequency of 2 or 2.7 percent. It revealed that the respondents were young adults. According to Erikson, 31-40 years old are considered young adults. Young adults need to form intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success leads to strong relationships, while failure results in loneliness and isolation. This stage covers the period of early adulthood when people are exploring personal relationships.

Sex. The majority of the respondents were female, with a frequency of 40 or 53.5 percent, followed by males, with a frequency of 35 or 46.7 percent. This shows that nursing is still a female-dominated profession to the present day. Through the efforts of Florence Nightingale in the mid-nineteenth century, nursing was established as a women's profession.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables
n=75

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	14	18.7
31 – 40	59	78.7
41 – 50	2	2.7
Sex		
Male	35	46.7
Female	40	53.3
Civil Status		
Single	38	50.7
Married	37	49.3
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	73	97.3
Master's Degree	1	1.3
Doctorate Degree	1	1.3
Number of Years in		

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Service in the Hemodialysis Center		
Below 1	5	6.7
1 – 2	29	38.7
3 – 4	31	41.3
5 and above	10	13.3
Number of Relevant Trainings on Hemodialysis for the Past Two Years		
0 – 1	26	34.7
2 – 3	44	58.7
4 – 5	2	2.7
6 or more	3	4.0
Health Facility		
Private	47	62.7
Public	28	37.3

Civil status. Most respondents were single, with a frequency of 38 or 50.7 percent, followed by married, with a frequency of 37 or 49.3 percent. This revealed that the respondents were not into marital relationships and were pursuing their experiences in their field of assignment.

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that most respondents were bachelor's degree holders with a frequency of 73 or 97.3 percent, followed by those with a MAN degree with a frequency of 1 or 1.3 percent, and doctorate degrees with a frequency of 1 or 1.3 percent. It showed that most respondents did not pursue a higher level of learning, which might be related to the fact that their salaries are not competitive, so some nurses fail to enroll in the master's or doctoral program.

Number of years in service. It showed that most respondents were in the service for 3-4 years, with a frequency of 31 or 41.3 percent; 1-2, with a frequency of 29 or 38.7 percent; and five years and above, with a frequency of 10 or 13.3 percent. It revealed that the respondents had been working in hemodialysis centers for a few years, having their experience in preparation for their certification as dialysis nurses.

Number of relevant trainings for the past two years. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents had undergone 2-3 training, with a frequency of 44 or 58.7 percent; those who had attended once, with a frequency of 26 or 34.7 percent; six and above, with a frequency of 3 or 4.0 percent, and 4-5 with a frequency of 2 or 2.7 percent. It reflects that the respondents have undergone a few relevant seminars on hemodialysis, which might be due to limited seminars during the pandemic, where accredited seminars are unavailable.

II. Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Patients

Table 2-4 presents the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among patients.

Table 2 presents the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among patients before hemodialysis.

Table 2
Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among
Patients Before Hemodialysis
n=75

Indicators	WM	TR
1. Training of nurses are required before handling or assisting in hemodialysis and education among.	4.88	HP
2. Donning of mask is done before hemodialysis.	4.84	HP
3. I clean my hands with waterless alcohol-based sanitizer or wash with soap and water before the start of dialysis session.	4.93	HP
4. I make sure optimal care of the access site is observed, such as using chlorhexidine gluconate for skin antisepsis, disinfecting CVC hubs before access.	4.91	HP
5. The water quality is strictly monitored before the procedure.	4.92	HP
6. Patients are checked if they are vaccinated against pneumococcal disease, influenza, and COVID-19.	4.81	HP
7. competency of nurses is periodically assessed to protect patients from avoidable harm.	4.89	HP
8. All surfaces of the dialysis station, including the machine and patient chair, are cleaned, and disinfected using hospital disinfectant.	4.91	HP
9. patients with hepa B, C, and tuberculosis to be treated are isolated to prevent transmission of infection to others.	4.99	HP
10. standard precautions are observed like use of personal protective equipment, respiratory hygiene, appropriate patient placement, careful handling of textiles and laundry, and safe injection practices.	4.95	HP
AWM	4.90	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced." However, the highest indicators are items numbers 3 and 5: "I clean my hands with waterless alcohol-based sanitizer or wash with soap and water before the start of the dialysis session," and "The water quality is strictly monitored before the procedure," with a weighted mean of 4.92 and 4.93, or "Highly Practiced."

It revealed that the nurses washed their hands or used disinfectants before assisting the patient with hemodialysis. Handwashing is simple yet necessary to eliminate microbes from the hands that might affect the patient. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2023), keeping hands clean is one of the most important steps to avoid getting sick and spreading germs to others. Not washing hands with soap and clean, running water spreads many diseases and conditions.

The lowest indicator is items numbers 2 and 6, "Patients are checked if they are vaccinated against pneumococcal disease, influenza, and COVID-19," and "Donning of the mask is done before hemodialysis," with a weighted mean of 4.81 and 4.84, or "Highly Practiced." It showed that the nurses checked for patients' vaccinations before hemodialysis. This practice will make them prevent the transmission of microbes from the patients. Wearing masks protects the nurses from transmission of microbes, particularly those aerobic types. According to Stepko (2020), it is essential to check for their vaccination since bacteria spreads when respiratory secretions (think saliva or mucus) are sent through the air by coughing or sneezing and then inhaling. Therefore, using masks is very important among health workers.

Overall, the preventive practices of nurses on nosocomial infection before hemodialysis got an average weighted mean of 4.90, or "Highly Practiced." implies that nurses should observe and practice different activities to prevent nosocomial infection before their patients' hemodialysis. Aside from that, hospitals have established infection tracking and surveillance systems with robust prevention strategies to reduce the rate of hospital-acquired infections.

The participant's response corroborates the study's findings that nurses perform prevention practices among patients undergoing hemodialysis. Nurses equally have skills in caring for patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Table 3 presents the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among patients during hemodialysis.

Table 3
Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among
Patients During Hemodialysis
n=75

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I perform skin preparation properly before the start of hemodialysis	4.92	HP
2. I properly use disposable gloves, eye goggles and other personal protective equipment during hemodialysis	4.91	HP
3. I monitor catheter insertion and ensure prompt removal, and careful attention to techniques for catheterization and catheter care.	4.96	HP
4. I make sure to prevent injuries from sharp instruments	4.95	HP
5. I properly dispose used needles in a closed unbreakable container with a "no touch technique"	4.99	HP
6. I attend to patient incidents and assist patient during hemodialysis	4.97	HP
7. I maintain hand hygiene and observe aseptic technique.	4.95	HP
8. Transmission-based precautions are observed to prevent spread of certain germs through direct or indirect contact, respiratory droplets, or airborne particles.	4.95	HP
9. I maintain a safe, clean, hygienic environment	4.99	HP
10. I use sterilized medical devices and decontamination of equipment	4.92	HP
AWM	4.95	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," however, the highest indicators are item numbers 5 and 9, "I properly dispose used needles in a closed unbreakable container with a "no touch technique," and "I maintain a safe, clean, hygienic environment," with a weighted mean of 4.99, or "Highly Practiced." It revealed that the nurses are careful enough in disposing of sharps and needles used during hemodialysis. It is considered contaminated and must be placed in trash bins for

used supplies. According to Piser (2021), sharps are biohazardous medical waste due to their ability to puncture, cut, or tear the skin and expose the injured party to contaminants.

This waste category is considered potentially harmful to humans and animals that come in contact with it, not only because of the risk of injury itself but also because of the potential exposure to dangerous pathogens from blood and other contaminated bodily fluids.

The lowest indicator is items numbers 2 and 10, "I properly use disposable gloves, eye goggles, and other personal protective equipment during hemodialysis," and "I use sterilized medical devices and decontamination of equipment," with a weighted mean of 4.91, and 4.92, or "Highly Practiced." It showed that the nurses observed proper disposal of used PPEs during the procedure. Equipment and tools used during hemodialysis must be placed in covered trash cans to avoid being invaded by flies and other insects, which might create contamination and affect other people.

Overall, the preventive practices of nurses on nosocomial infection during hemodialysis got an average weighted mean of 4.95, or "Highly Practiced." implying that the nurses maintain an aseptic technique and properly dispose of used supplies and PPEs. According to the United States Food and Drugs, Personal Protective Equipment is a barrier between infectious materials such as viral and bacterial contaminants and the skin, mouth, nose, or eyes (mucous membranes). The barrier could block the transmission of contaminants from blood, body fluids, or respiratory secretions.

Moreover, Table 4 presents the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among patients after hemodialysis.

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," however, the highest indicators are items numbers 3 and 10, "I monitor vital signs and weigh patients after hemodialysis," and "I clean and disinfect dialysis equipment after use," with a weighted mean of 4.96, and 4.97 or "Highly Practiced." It revealed that the nurses monitored and assessed the patients after the procedure. This stage is vital to check patients' condition after hemodialysis to safeguard them from possible complications. According to Brekke (2019), vital signs play an important role in determining patients at risk of deterioration. Even though vital sign changes accurately predict it, clinical deterioration often goes unnoticed or is not detected until it is too late to treat.

The lowest indicator is item numbers 1 and 5, "I disinfect the internal surfaces of the dialysis machine after the hemodialysis," and "I segregate linens, gowns and other textiles used during the procedure," with a weighted mean of 4.87, or "Highly Practiced." It showed that the nurses perform aftercare on the equipment and tools used during the procedure. They segregate the supplies according to their category since they are cleaned and sterilized accordingly.

Table 4
Practices of Health Workers in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among
Patients After Hemodialysis
n=75

Indicators	WM	TR
1. I disinfect the internal surfaces of the dialysis machine after the hemodialysis	4.87	HP
2. I handle blood samples and other specimens strictly before submitting to the laboratory	4.91	HP
3. I monitor vital signs and weigh patients after hemodialysis	4.96	HP
4. I properly dispose used mask, gloves, and other materials after hemodialysis	4.93	HP
5. I segregate linens, gowns and other textiles used during the procedure	4.87	HP
6. I assess the signs and symptoms of infection after hemodialysis	4.95	HP
7. I observe the risks associated with catheters after the procedure	4.92	HP
8. I respond immediately if problems with the catheter develop in the dialysis center	4.93	HP
9. I discuss access care at home (e.g., bathing with a catheter) to the patient and significant others	4.92	HP
10. I clean and disinfect dialysis equipment after use	4.97	HP
AWM	4.92	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Overall, nurses' preventive practices on nosocomial infection after hemodialysis got an average weighted mean of 4.92, or "Highly Practiced." This implies that the nurses were aware of and practiced aftercare of the equipment used in preparation for the following patients to undergo the procedure, as well as the readiness and functionality of the equipment. Potential risks of this type of dialysis include infection, poor blood flow, blockage from scar tissue, blood clots, anemia, and sudden heart attack.

Participant No. 4 Myra

After the procedure, "I prepare the patient for transfer to his bed to monitor vital signs. Once stable, the specimen samples are labeled, and I send them to the laboratory. Patients with infectious illnesses are separated from the others. Then, I wash and cleanse

the tools used and prepare them for sterilization. All the used Personal Protective Equipment is discarded immediately and placed in a closed container. If problems occur, we respond immediately to prevent complications."

It revealed that the participant nurse's narration corroborates the study's findings. The nurses have standard practices in caring for patients undergoing hemodialysis, which shows that they are competent.

Additionally, Table 5 presents the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among patients.

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," however, the highest period given the highest aspect is during dialysis, with a weighted mean of 4.95, or "Highly Practiced." This implies that the nurses consider hemodialysis to be the most important because this is when the patient is undergoing the procedure and needs more attention and monitoring.

Table 5
Summary of Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection
among Hemodialysis Patients
n=75

Aspect	WM	TR
Before Hemodialysis	4.90	HP
During Hemodialysis	4.95	HP
After Hemodialysis	4.92	HP
OWM	4.92	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

The lowest aspect is long before and after dialysis; both are rated "Highly Practiced," with a weighted mean of 4.0 and 4.92. It revealed that the nurses equally practiced preventing nosocomial infection among the patients. Regardless of the hemodialysis period, nurses maintain their utmost care and concern to ensure that nothing happens to the patients while they are in the dialysis center.

Overall, nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients got an overall weighted mean of 4.92, or "Highly Practiced." This revealed that

nurses do what is right and proper in preventing nosocomial infection among patients undergoing hemodialysis. Nursing is a caring profession, and nurses know their responsibilities during the procedure.

Part III. Results Stressing the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Profile Variables

Table 6-15 presents the results of the difference in the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across profile variables.

Table 6 presents the results of the difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients of different ages.

Table 6
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.494	2	.247	7.339	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	2.425	72	.034			
	Total	2.919	74				
During Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.427	2	.213	12.576	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	1.221	72	.017			
	Total	1.647	74				
After Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.408	2	.204	8.934	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	1.644	72	.023			
	Total	2.051	74				

The computed F-values generated significance values lower than the set .05 level of significance; hence, the results are significant. This means that nurses' age affects their practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients before, during, and after hemodialysis. The table on the next page reveals the age groups that significantly differ in their extent of practice.

Table 7 presents the significant difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients of different ages.

Table 7
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Age

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Before Hemodialysis	21-30 vs 41-50	.400	.020
	31-40 vs 41-50	.481	.002
During Hemodialysis	21-30 vs 41-50	.436	.000
	31-40 vs 41-50	.468	.000
After Hemodialysis	21-30 vs 41-50	.386	.045
	31-40 vs 41-50	.446	.001

It is evident in the significant mean differences of their positive values, which indicate that the nurses in the younger health bracket have higher levels of practice in preventing nosocomial infections than those in the older age bracket. It revealed that the younger nurses had more prevention practices because they were still getting their experiences and were more aggressive in giving their care to patients.

Table 8 shows the difference in the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across sexes.

Table 8
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Sex

Aspect	Sex	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Male	35	4.93	.043	.046	73	.939	.351	Not Significant
	Female	40	4.88						
During Hemodialysis	Male	35	4.96	.015	.035	73	.422	.675	Not Significant
	Female	40	4.94						
After Hemodialysis	Male	35	4.93	.011	.039	73	.286	.776	Not Significant
	Female	40	4.92						

The computed t-values provided significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance, hence insignificant results. This implies that the nurses' sex does not affect their practices in preventing nosocomial infections. Nurses, regardless of their gender, render the same practices in preventing nosocomial infections. Daily exposure to these types of patients made them more competent in caring for hemodialysis patients.

Table 9 displays the difference in the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across civil status.

Table 9
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Civil Status

Aspect	Civil Status	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Single	38	4.86	-.096	.045	73	-2.145	.035	Significant
	Married	37	4.95						
During Hemodialysis	Single	38	4.91	-.073	.034	73	-2.181	.032	Significant
	Married	37	4.99						
After Hemodialysis	Single	38	4.87	-.099	.037	73	-2.688	.009	Significant
	Married	37	4.97						

The computed t-values have corresponding significance values lower than the set .05 significance level suggests significant differences in the practices before, during, and after hemodialysis.

The significant negative mean difference indicates that married health workers provide more practice in preventing nosocomial infections.

Likewise, Table 10 reveals the difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across the highest educational attainment.

Table 10
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.833	2	.417	14.377	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	2.086	72	.029			
	Total	2.919	74				
During Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.915	2	.457	44.956	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	.733	72	.010			
	Total	1.647	74				
After Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.534	2	.267	12.666	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	1.518	72	.021			
	Total	2.051	74				

The computed F-values provided significance values at the set .05 significance level. This indicates the existence of significant differences in nurses' practices before, during, and after hemodialysis, specifically in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients. Furthermore, nurses' educational backgrounds significantly affect such practices. It implies that those with higher educational attainment practice more in preventing nosocomial infection.

Moreover, Table 11 presents the significant difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across the highest educational attainment.

Table 11
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Before Hemodialysis	Bachelor's Degree vs Doctorate Degree	.914	.000
During Hemodialysis	Bachelor's Degree vs Doctorate Degree	.962	.000
After Hemodialysis	Bachelor's Degree vs Doctorate Degree	.732	.000

The results of the Scheffe Test reveal that nurses who finished their Bachelor's degree have significantly higher levels of practice in preventing nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis than the respondent who has a doctorate implies that even nurses who earned Bachelor's degrees showed their competencies in preventing nosocomial infection in patients undergoing dialysis. They are the ones in direct contact with patients. Thereby, they have mastery in handling hemodialysis patients.

Table 12 shows the difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across the number of years they have been in service in the hemodialysis center.

Table 12
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Number of Years in Service in the Hemodialysis Center

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.244	3	.081	2.160	.100	Not Significant
	Within Groups	2.675	71	.038			
	Total	2.919	74				
During Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.124	3	.041	1.933	.132	Not Significant
	Within Groups	1.523	71	.021			
	Total	1.647	74				
After Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.235	3	.078	3.068	.033	Significant
	Within Groups	1.816	71	.026			
	Total	2.051	74				

The computed F-value with significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance before and during hemodialysis shows no significant difference across the number of years in service.

This means that nurses, regardless of their number of years in service, follow the same practices for preventing nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis.

Meanwhile, significant differences exist after hemodialysis. This means that the number of years of service affects nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection after hemodialysis. Table 13 shows the results of the Scheffe test on this aspect.

Table 13 displays the significant difference in the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across several years of service in the hemodialysis center.

Table 13
Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Patients across Number of Years in Service in the Hemodialysis Center

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
After Hemodialysis	Below 1 vs 1-2	-.174	.027
	Below 1 vs 3-4	-.201	.011

The significant negative mean difference reveals that the nurses with greater length of service have better practices in preventing nosocomial infection after hemodialysis. It revealed that the longer the nurses have been in service, the more they

have mastered the prevention of nosocomial infection for patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Table 14 presents the difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across a number of relevant trainings.

Table 14
ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Patients across Number of Relevant Trainings on Hemodialysis for the Past Two Years

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.191	3	.064	1.657	.184	Not Significant
	Within Groups	2.728	71	.038			
	<i>Total</i>	2.919	74				
During Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.011	3	.004	.164	.921	Not Significant
	Within Groups	1.636	71	.023			
	<i>Total</i>	1.647	74				
After Hemodialysis	Between Groups	.064	3	.021	.762	.519	Not Significant
	Within Groups	1.988	71	.028			
	<i>Total</i>	2.051	74				

The computed F-values have significance values higher than the set .05 significance level. Hence, no significant difference exists.

The number of relevant nursing training sessions does not affect their practices in preventing nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis. The study revealed that the nurses performed comparable performances in preventing nosocomial infection regardless of the number of training sessions.

Table 15 displays the difference in nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients across categories of health facilities.

Table 15
t-Test Results on the Difference in the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients across Health Facility

Aspect	Category	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	Df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Before Hemodialysis	Private	47	4.89	-.036	.048	73	-.749	.456	Not Significant
	Public	28	4.93						
During Hemodialysis	Private	47	4.95	-.007	.036	73	-.189	.851	Not Significant
	Public	28	4.95						
After Hemodialysis	Private	47	4.90	-.072	.039	73	-1.843	.069	Not Significant
	Public	28	4.97						

The computed t-values provided significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance; hence, the results are not significant. The type of health facility that the nurses are affiliated with does not affect their practices in preventing nosocomial infections among hemodialysis patients.

It revealed that the nurses in any health care facility category render comparable practices in preventing nosocomial infection.

Part IV. Relationship Between the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients and their Profile Variables

Table 16 displays the relationship between the practices of nurses in preventing nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients and their profile variables.

Significant positive R-values are evident between practices and highest educational attainment.

Nurses are given the chance to be with a significant other and engage in good practices in preventing nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis.

Table 16
Relationship Between the Practices of Nurses in Preventing Nosocomial Infection among Hemodialysis Patients and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Before Hemodialysis		During Hemodialysis		After Hemodialysis	
	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig
Age	-.026	.823	-.147	.208	-.061	.603
Sex	-.109	.351	-.049	.675	-.033	.776
Civil Status	.243*	.035	.247*	.032	.300*	.009
Highest Educational Attainment	-.453*	.000	-.652*	.000	-.432*	.000
Number of Years in Service in Hemodialysis Center	-.095	.417	.105	.370	.056	.631
Number of Relevant Trainings	-.074	.530	.038	.749	-.022	.848
Health Facility	.087	.456	.022	.851	.211	.069

*Significant at .05 level

On the other hand, significant negative R-values are evident between practices and the highest educational attainment, indicating an inverse relationship. The lower the level of educational attainment of the nurses, the more they practice the proper prevention of nosocomial infection before and after hemodialysis, implying that even those with a bachelor's degree should practice the correct methods to prevent nosocomial infection. No other significant relationship is established between the practices of nurses and other profile variables.

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM AMONG NURSES

General objectives: To enhance the nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infections among hemodialysis patients.

- A. Intensify the monitoring of vaccinations received by patients undergoing hemodialysis. Therefore, prior to the procedure, the HD staff will conduct pre-dialysis orientation among watchers or patients. They will be provided with brochures on instructions prior to hemodialysis, and instructions will be specified.
- B. The proper use of personal protective equipment before the procedure must be strictly implemented. Each patient or watcher entering the hemodialysis unit must wear personal protective equipment and work with the hemodialysis team.
- C. Improve support services for patients. Hemodialysis patients must be assisted throughout the procedure for them to be cooperative and gain confidence.
- D. Enhancing the quality-of-care services the treatment team provides, upgrading the facilities and equipment. The HD team must report properly to management to have regular maintenance and procure updated HD equipment.
- E. Adoption of an interdisciplinary approach to improve the care services among in-patients receiving hemodialysis treatment. Proper coordination with the staff nurses when the patient is admitted to the hospital is necessary to avoid delays or unpreparedness before the procedure.
- F. Interventions to promote employees' health and well-being must be included in the planning of activities of the hospital.
- G. Educational interventions to develop healthy behaviors in hemodialysis patients to help patients adapt to disease, treatment, and behavioral changes. Health education is organized for family members so that they will understand the nature of their patient's condition.
- H. Development of a training program for hemodialysis nurses

Certificate in Hemodialysis Program

- theoretical Phase
- clinical Phase

Continuing Education program in hemodialysis

Advanced training in Dialysis

Proposed Training program for Hemodialysis Nurses in Evidence-Based Exploration of infection prevention practices.

General Objectives: To further enhance Hemodialysis Nurses for evidence-based exploration of infection prevention practices.

TYPE OF TRAINING	OBJECTIVES	TIMETABLE
Safe Access Healthy Outcomes Hemodialysis Infection Control	To determine the different ways of hemodialysis infection control.	July 2024
Safe Needles Healthy Lives Hemodialysis Infection Practices	To enhance the safe needle practices of nurses among hemodialysis patients	September 2024
Infection Warriors Hemodialysis Nurse Preparedness	To ensure the preparedness of nurses to prevent infection among hemodialysis patients.	November 2024
Clean Hands Safe Care Hemodialysis Infection Control	To teach the importance of hand hygiene in the care of hemodialysis patients.	January 2025

Proposed Training Program for Hemodialysis Nurses in Infection and Prevention

General Objectives: To further enhance Hemodialysis Nurse’s for exploring infection prevention practices.

Training to enhance the nurses in infection control among hemodialysis patients.

Dialysis Shield Strengthening Infection Control Measures	To introduce other measures of strengthening infection control.	May 2025
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Conclusions

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the study's findings.

Based on the study's findings, the following are now concluded.

1. The nurse respondents were young adults, female-dominated, with a bachelor's degree. They had been in the dialysis center for 3-4 years, attended a few seminars, and were employed in private dialysis centers.
The nurses interviewed were adults, males, and females, mostly holders of Bachelor's degrees, who have been in the service for more years and work equally in public and private HD centers.
2. The extent of nurses' practices in the prevention of nosocomial infection among hemodialysis patients is highest during hemodialysis, followed by after hemodialysis, and lowest before dialysis.
The nurses interviewed corroborated with the practices done by those in the quantitative aspect.
3. Married nurses significantly practice more effectively in preventing nosocomial infection than single nurses. The number of years of service also affects nurses' practices in preventing nosocomial infection after hemodialysis.
4. The lower the nurses' highest educational attainment, the more they practice the proper prevention of nosocomial infection before, during, and after hemodialysis, implying that even those with Bachelor's degrees should practice the correct way to prevent nosocomial infection.
5. The proposed intervention program is prepared to enhance the prevention practices of nosocomial infection.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions formulated, the following are at this moment offered:

1. in the quantitative aspect, both nurse respondents must continue to pursue a higher level of learning and attend relevant hemodialysis seminars.
2. To improve their prevention practices, The respondents must enhance their prevention practices, particularly before and after hemodialysis.

3. Regardless of their profile variables, the nurses must improve their prevention practices in all three periods of hemodialysis.
4. Young nurses and other nurses must continue their prevention practices for nosocomial infection to benefit those hemodialysis patients.
5. The proposed intervention program can be adapted for implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher diligently ensured adherence to ethical precautions and procedures throughout the study. These included:

Respect for Patient Autonomy

It involves obtaining informed consent from participants or their legal representatives, ensuring comprehension of the research purpose, risks, and benefits, and respecting participants' right to refuse or withdraw from the study without repercussions.

Confidentiality and Privacy

Includes protecting the confidentiality of participant information, utilizing secure data storage and transmission methods, and ensuring that research data is accessible only to authorized personnel.

Beneficence and non-maleficence

Includes implementing appropriate measures to protect participants from physical or psychological harm, providing necessary support services, and promptly addressing any adverse events or concerns.

Transparency and Disclosure

Includes communicating the study's purpose, objectives, and methodology to participants, disclosing any potential conflicts of interest, and providing accurate information about using and disseminating research findings.

Fair Treatment and Equity

Includes avoiding discrimination or bias in participant selection, accommodating diverse needs and backgrounds, and fostering an inclusive research environment.

Professional Integrity

Includes maintaining honesty and accuracy in data collection and reporting, avoiding fabrication or falsification of results, and acknowledging any limitations or biases in the research findings.

Accountability and Oversight

This will involve regularly monitoring and auditing research protocols, reporting ethical concerns or violations, and cooperating with investigations or inquiries.

Participant Advocacy

Includes addressing participant concerns or grievances, ensuring access to necessary resources or support services, and promoting a culture of respect and dignity in research settings.

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